

MUSE Standard Sensor Interface

Project: MUSE Standard Sensor Interface

Author: Jan Fleer, Danilo Scheppukat, Christian Katlein

Date	17.05.2024
-------------	-------------------

Creator	Jan Fleer (Geomar), Christian Katlein (AWI), Danilo Scheppukat (Geomar)
E-Mail	ckatlein@awi.de
Phone	-

Version			
Version:	Date:	Name:	Changes:
0.1	05.05.2023	Fleer Jan	First Draft
0.2	22.01.2024	Scheppukat, Danilo	Gendertype „Male“ DBH13 changed to „Female“ (all Bulkheads from devices should be “Female”) General corrections
0.3	05.02.2024	Christian Katlein	Adaptation to MUSE Standard
0.4	17.05.2024	Christian Katlein	Preparation of Draft for publication, specifying 8 Pin MCBH as standard connector for serial.

--	--

regarding	Vermerk
------------------	----------------

Content	This document contains the standards of the connector pinouts for MUSE infrastructure based on the standard of the Technik- und Logistikzentrum at the GEOMAR. The standardization enables a higher modularisation of the deep-sea devices and systems at the GEOMAR, HEREON and AWI. This standard is to be used for MUSE funded infrastructure wherever possible.
----------------	---

Contents

1	Standardization of the connector pinout	4
2	Connector type	5
2.1	Ethernet DBH-13F	5
2.2	Power	7
2.2.1	BH4-F (TI/SS)*	8
2.2.2	MCBH5-F	8
2.3	Lights MCBH3-F	9
2.4	Serial	6
2.4.1	MCBH5-F	7
2.4.2	MCBH8-F	6

1 Standardization of the connector pinout

Objective and Organization:

The general target is to standardize the connections of sensors and payloads to the devices and systems (AUVS, ROVS, instruments, etc.) for underwater robotic systems at AWI Geomar and Hereon. Furthermore, the standardization is intended to increase modularity and distribute central competencies.

If all devices have the same plug assignments, it is easy to exchange and share devices on expeditions. In addition, the risk of damaging a device is lower as power supplies are the same for all devices and systems.

Using the same pin assignment for standard plugs makes cooperation between institutes much easier. Concentrating on a set of underwater connectors can make it easier to keep spares ready.

Existing systems can often be made MUSE compatible with adapter Plugs. These can be purchased within the MUSE project Task 2.

The MUSE Standard concentrates on interfaces between vehicle payloads (particularly sensors, samplers, cameras, etc...); other connectors may be used in between vehicle components

System Voltage:

Wherever possible, 24V DC supply voltage should be used. If deviating from this standard it should be labeled on the bulkheads or sensors.

Any deviation from MUSE pinout should be labeled accordingly. Female connectors to be used on the platform (ROV/AUV/... side). Cable colors may depend on manufacturer, so Pin numbers are essential.

Connector options:

The standard defines sometimes several Connector pin amounts for GEOMAR legacy reasons, but specifies which one should be preferred for new applications.

THIS IS A STANDARD SPECIFICATION UNDER CONTINUOUS DEVELOPMENT AND WILL BE AMENDED AND ADAPTED IN THE FUTURE

2 Connector type

2.1 Ethernet DBH-13F

Pin	Color	use
1	black	power -
2	orange	screen
3	White	power +
4	brown*	1Gbit TIA-B
5	brown/white*	1Gbit TIA-B
6	blue*	1Gbit TIA-B
7	blue/white*	1Gbit TIA-B
8	orange*	1Gbit TIA-B
9	orange/white*	1Gbit TIA-B
10	green*	1Gbit TIA-B
11	green/white*	1Gbit TIA-B
12	red	optional***
13	green	optional***

* twisted pairs,

** 1Gbit TIA-

*** no default, please check the use of other Teams, if pins are connected it needs to be labelled on the device/platform

2.2 Serial

2.2.1 MCBH8-F (MUSE preferred)

Pin	Color	use
1	black	power -
2	white	power +
3	Red	Optional *
4	green	TxD (1)
5	orange	RxD (1)
6	Blue	TxD (2)
7	White/black	RxD (2)
8	Red/black	Optional*

TxD (1) RS-232 (1) / RS-485 (1) / RS-422

RxD (1) RS-232 (1) / RS-485 (1) / RS-422

TxD (2) RS-232 (2) / RS-485 (2) / RS-422

RxD (2) RS-232 (2) / RS-485 (2) / RS-422

*no default, please check the use of other Teams, if pins are connected it needs to be labelled on the device/platform

Connectivity on the 4 Serial Lines is somewhat flexible to allow e.g. RS-485 full duplex communication for special applications. However, the following pinout is recommended for standard MUSE interfaces:

MUSE platforms pinout further spec: (Implementation on TPS ROV)

Pin	Color	use
1	black	power - GND
2	white	power +24V
3	Red	Optional *
4	green	TxD (1, RS232)
5	orange	RxD (1, RS232)
6	Blue	TxD (2, RS485 A)
7	White/black	RxD (2, RS485 B))
8	Red/black	Optional*

2.2.2 MCBH5-F (only for legacy compatibility with GEOMAR equipment)

Pin	Color	use
1	black	power -
2	white	power +
3	Red	Optional *
4	green	TxD (1)
5	orange	RxD (1)

TxD (1) RS-232 / RS-485

RxD (1) RS-232 / RS-485

*no default, please check the use of other Teams, if pins are connected it needs to be labelled on the device/platform

2.3 Power

2.3.1 BH4-F (Ti/SS)*

Pin	Color	use
1	black	power -
2	white	power +
3	Red	power -
4	green	power +

*Ti = Titan / SS = stainless steel

2.3.2 MCBH5-F

Pin	Color	use
1	black	power -
2	white	power +
3	Red	
4	green	
5	orange	

2.4 Lights MCBH3-F

Pin	Color	use
1	black	power -
2	white	power +
3	red	Optional*

* Light control (0-5V/PWM), if pins are connected it needs to be labelled on the device/platform

3 Implementation of standard serial sentence \$MUS

This standard also defines a standard serial sentence. MUSE compatible platforms will be able to log and interact with these.

- Self describing NMEA interface both on RS232/RS485
- Baud Rate: 115200 (?), ASCII
- Standard Stop/Parity/...
- `$MUS,$MUS_substandard, NameToTelemetry, ValueToTelemetry, CommandToPlatform, Name1,Value1,Name2,Value2,...<CR><LF>`
- `$MUS_substandard` enables a platform to know which sensor type is connected
- `NameToTelemetry` is the Name of a scalar numerical or text `ValueToTelemetry` that shall be forwarded to topside. This can be commands to vehicles, Sensor values needed for decision making or other. Muse Platforms can read, record (and forward) this message. If not used, it is to be left empty. E.g.
- The other Name Value pairs are for recording of data. `$MUS,$MUS_substandard,,,, Name1,...`

If possible platforms shall be able to record and forward these messages. It is the goal to develop a ROS node for this interface.

If you have questions or remarks, do not hesitate to contact ckatlein@awi.de